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Frantz Fanon and the Critique of Colonialism: A Philosophical Inquiry

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Abstract

The question of colonialism has been a deteriorating phenomenon in African history. Frantz Fanon conceived colonialism as a form of domination with the goal redefining the reality of the world of indigenous (“native”) peoples, which he considered possible through the means of violence. His conception of colonialism is that which with no doubt is embedded in vices and nothing more irrespective of the claims of the colonial masters that they aim at civilizing the people of Africa. Exploitation, extortion, economic stagnancy, regression, and many more vices were all recorded as effects of colonialism. It involves the domination of a set of people in their society by different people known as settlers from another society, promoting class distinction and dehumanization. In a bid to evaluate its effect and impact both on the dominated society and the settlers’ society (nation), Fanon also enters into the discussion

as he criticizes the idea of colonialism from his perspective, thereby accentuating possible solutions. This work thereby exposes Fanon's critique of colonialism, and its' possible effects if and when followed as proposed by the colonial masters. Using Conceptual and critical analysis, this paper argues that Fanon's revolutionary model must be reassessed, as contemporary struggles for liberation demand more than armed resistance considering the shift in realities

Keywords: Colonialism, Decolonisation, Fanon, Neocolonialism, Violence

Introduction

Colonialism is one of the ugliest experiences in African history, which left an imprint on her political, economic, and cultural realities. Colonialism is an experience that was perpetuated by European countries. This experience was exerted as a form of forced domination, which was not only an exploitative system but also a mechanism for cultural alteration and identity redefinition. This control exerted is beyond their (European) traditional borders over. According to expression of Peterson (2021), colonialism is argued to be a form of domination whose purpose is to reorder the world of indigenous people, often enforced through coercion, forced labor, and exploitation, all of which involve the use of violence. Similarly, Borocz and Sarkar (2012) define colonialism as the domination of a society by settlers from a different society. The experience of colonialism has always been ugly, inhumane, and dehumanizing for those subjected to it. It embodies an exploitative and oppressive system in which colonial masters regarded the colonized as slaves, objects for exploitation, and mere tools for realizing the goals of their mother states. However, some critics took a different stand, trying to whitewash colonialism as having a positive effect, only to withdraw their position upon thorough reconsideration. According to Parashar and Schulz (2019), colonialism was not merely an event but a disruptive force that altered the development, peace, and progress of the territories subjected to it. They are of the view that colonialism affected not only the political, economic, and cultural aspects of colonized societies, such as Africa, but also psychologically dominated them, whereby there is a sense of inferiority embraced by the colonized, and a sense of superiority associated with the colonial masters. Further speaking on this psychological domination, Walter Rodney (1972) in his book 'How Europe Underdeveloped

Africa,' explains how African people were compelled, particularly by missionaries, who served as instruments of colonial control, to internalize ideologies that justified their subjugation. For example, they were taught to sing All Things Bright and Beautiful, which included verses suggesting that colonial masters were divinely ordained to rule, while the colonized were destined to serve as slaves. This psychological manipulation reinforced a sense of helplessness and submission, making colonized peoples more susceptible to forced labor, dehumanization, and colonial influence, which was imposed through brute force and violence.

Given the violent nature of colonial rule, Frantz Fanon (1961), in *The Wretched of the Earth*, advocated for violent resistance, arguing that colonial masters would not willingly relinquish power since they had gained control through force. Therefore, Fanon contended that decolonization must also involve the same level of force to reclaim autonomy and dismantle the exploitative colonial structures. His approach provided a radical analysis of how colonialism dehumanized the colonized, portraying it as a system that thrives on both physical and psychological oppression. His works, particularly *The Wretched of the Earth*, have remained central to post-colonial discourse, exposing the violence embedded in the colonial structure and advocating for revolutionary resistance as the path to liberation. This paper explores Fanon's critique of colonialism, particularly the ways in which colonial rule systematically displaced African identity and demonized indigenous traditions. Colonialism was not just an economic system but a psychological war, redefining the identity of the colonized and subjecting them to cultural subjugation. Through the missionary system, colonial rulers effectively replaced indigenous religious and cultural frameworks with Western ideologies, portraying African traditions as barbaric and inferior while glorifying European beliefs. However, despite the political independence of African states, the psychological effects of colonialism persist, influencing modern governance and socio-political structures.

This paper thus critically examines Fanon's arguments, particularly his justification of revolutionary violence and its implications for contemporary post-colonial societies. While Fanon viewed violence as an inevitable response to colonial oppression, questions remain about its effectiveness in achieving long-term stability and tenability, considering the geopolitics of today. The focus will be on assessing whether his call for armed resistance is still relevant in today's world. The method embraced herein is textual

analysis of Fanon's works, focusing primarily on *The Wretched of the Earth*. Secondary sources, including academic articles and historical accounts, will be examined to contextualize his critique of colonialism within broader post-colonial debates. A comparative approach will also be applied, drawing parallels between Fanon's revolutionary framework and the lived realities of post-independence African states. This paper argues that Fanon's critique of colonialism remains relevant, particularly in its analysis of cultural domination and psychological alienation, for the impact of colonial rule continues to influence and determine African realities. However, his revolutionary model must be reassessed, as contemporary struggles for liberation demand more than armed resistance.

Conceptual Clarification

The Concept of Colonialism

The term colonialism refers to a "...large-scale political and economic system that allows one geopolitical entity (such as a nation-state or city-state) to establish controls beyond its traditional geographic borders in the service of increased profit or power" (Ahuja, 2017: 237). The term is coined out of the English word 'colony', while the English word colony is derived from the ancient Latin term *colonia*, which interprets to be an outpost or settlement. In other words, colonialism etymologically means "...the domination of a society by settlers from a different society" (Borocz & Sarkar, 2012: 1). There undeniable fact is that colonialism is an ugly experience any nation would ever experience considering its inhuman and destructive effect on the people's well-being. Colonialism have so far been documented to occur in many nations but specifically huge on the African soil. No doubt, African countries have been the most suffered colonies of colonialism for we have over time been tagged as humans without rationality and some even classified us as being fewer humans. Howbeit, there came to be lots of African leaders who have shouldered the responsibility of breaking the chain of colonialism without considering consequences of their actions on their personal well-being: on the like of, Frantz Fanon Leopold Sedar Senghor, Kwame Nkrumah, Julius Nyerere, Nnamdi Azikiwe, Obafemi Awolowo, among many others. However, their responses to colonialism differed due to their experience of it in different ways.

Colonialism could be considered to be a form of domination whose necessary goal for success was the reordering of the world of indigenous ("native")

people, with the use of violence (Peterson, 2021). However, the colonial masters involved in this act have over the year justified their every action by Euro-centrism. They are of the view that they are superior to every other race and because of that warrant their interference with every other nation in order to save them from the wilderness into being civilized. To be factual with, Colonialism came with racism, segregation, and alongside violence and, many other inhuman and devastating experiences. Colonialism has been confirmed to be direct form of imperialism. This explains the reason behind the assertion that all colonialisms are imperialism but not all imperialisms are colonialism. As portrayed above, the African continent did suffer the most in the hands of colonialism. Specifically, as opposed to the insinuation that colonialism aims at civilizing a less civilized nation, colonialism manifest itself in two prospects which has to do with the seizure of the political power and the embark on exploitation in order to make the work easier and faster. However, exploitation and extortion remain the major goal of colonialism. Thus:

Colonialism is the direct and overall domination of one country by another on the basis of state power being in the hands of a foreign power (For example, the direct and overall domination of Nigeria by Britain between 1900-1960). The first objective of colonialism is political domination. Its second objective is to make possible the exploitation of the colonized country (Ocheni & Nwankwo, 2012: 47).

To deduce from the above, colonialism has no positive intention neither is it legal, but negative and ill perpetuated towards its colony because “European colonial expansion was an inherently violent affair. By laying the groundwork for profitable transoceanic trades in minerals, agricultural commodities, manufactured goods, and enslaved human laborers...” (Ahuja, 2017: 239). Colonialism was initiated by the western states, and the two major hosts on the African soil are the British and the French masters. They believed their actions are justified on the grounds that they are superior to every other race which in turn, means their right to rule over others. The British masters employed the indirect rule system in its colonial affairs, while the French masters made us of the policy of assimilation system to control, manage, and direct the affairs of its’ colonies. Colonialism without doubt turned and influenced every state it comes in contact with, for “...colonialism allowed the Spanish, Portuguese, Dutch, British, French, and Belgian monarchies to enrich themselves and to engage in ever-more

intense economic and military competition with one another” (Ahuja, 2017: 239), and leads to inhuman extortion of their colonies.

The meaning of colonialism has been classified into two strands, which, in essence, represent definitions based on practice and worldview. As a practice, colonialism involves the domination of one society by settlers from another. As a worldview, it is a global geopolitical, economic, and cultural doctrine rooted in the worldwide expansion of Western European capitalism, which persisted even after the collapse of most colonial empires (Borocz & Sarkar, 2012: 1). However, upon closer examination, the first definition serves as the cause of the second. In other words, colonialism as a practice directly led to the emergence of colonialism as a worldview. Hence, the latter can be interpreted as the effect of the former. According to Borocz and Sarkar (2012) highlight, colonialism had a devastating impact on African states, contributing to the economic advancement of Western Europe at the expense of the colonized. It systematically dismantled the social, legal, political, and economic structures of indigenous societies. This process involved imperial warfare, which led to the displacement and mass killings of indigenous populations, as well as the destruction of their technologies, trade networks, and economic institutions. Colonizers imposed foreign legal systems, replacing communal land ownership with private property laws to facilitate taxation on agricultural production (Borocz & Sarkar, 2012: 2).

To the above effect, it is open and clear that colonialism only came into being out of selfish desires and quest for power and control, over other states that appears weaker. Hence, it is deducible that colonialism has psychological effect, physical effect and as well structural effect. Not positive effects as the colonial masters will claim, but that that which is embedded in vice because “... it involved the superimposition of the rule of an alien social order on another, violence inhered in all aspects of colonialism” (Borocz & Sarkar, 2012: 2). This is so because no sane nation will willingly relinquish its freedom to an external control in the name of civilization. This explains why Aimé Césaire compared colonialism with the European experience when he pointed out that colonialism allowed the routine practice of all elements of what later came to be regarded as Nazi violence within Europe, on non-European populations overseas ((Borocz & Sarkar, 2012). Arguably, Colonialism is responsible for most of the setbacks being experienced by

many African countries till date because its influence goes beyond just physical enslavement, but as well psychological and structural.

Modern Day Colonialism (Neo-colonialism)

The term Neo-colonialism is a version of colonialism but manifest in a different form, but with the same motives and intention with colonialism. The term 'neo-colonialism' primarily refers to the actions and influences of former colonial powers within a postcolonial society. It has been established by scholars to be an already planned sabotage by the colonial masters before their partial departure to their respective homeland, however, some newly emerged powerful nations have been recorded to join the movement. Historically,

The term Neocolonialism is believed to first have been ascribed by Ghana's first president Kwame Nkrumah, who mentioned it in his foreword at the Organization of African States Charter (OAU) in 1963 but got international attention by publishing his book "Neo-colonialism: The Last Stage of Imperialism" in 1965 (Khodadadzadeh, 2017: 13).

This parasitic phenomenon as many will classify it to be have been so much successful through many already planned medium installed by the colonial masters, of which capitalism is one of them. Mudimbe exposed that it (neo-colonialism) had been the arrangement of the West from the revelation of African state and her natural resources. As observed by Nkrumah, the principle of Neo-colonialism consists of states that are officially autonomous but has its political policy and economy dependent and controlled by foreign political and economic influences (Haag, 2011:9, Nkrumah, 1965:7). He believed that colonial arrangements made on the African consciousness made Neo-colonialism easier and even more successful than colonialism itself because it can last forever if care is not taken because:

it generally represents the actions and effects of certain remnant features and agents of the colonial era in a given society. Post-colonial studies have shown extensively that despite achieving independence, the influences of colonialism and its agents are still very much present in the lives of most former colonies (Afsi, 2017: 1)

It is evident that Neo-colonialism is an advanced form of colonialism because colonialism became outdated, but Neo-colonialism can however last forever and is very much more effective than colonialism. The discourse on

neo-colonialism are major discourse in African philosophy because, Africa is one of the leading continent under the torment of neo-colonialism. This in itself explains the reason why neo-colonialism was first expressed in the work of Kwame Nkrumah. Historically, Neo-colonialism can be traced back to the demise of colonialism after World War II. This left the colonial states incapable to contain their colonies and hereby left with the choice to withdraw. Hence, they were forced to put some things in place since their goal is nothing other than exploitation, and so by implication won't be letting off the grip of the African resources. In essence, arrangements are made to continually extort and exploit their colonies even without their direct presence therein. Hence, they attempted all forms of enslavement from the structural, to the mental, down to the physical aspect of the African lives. Also, colonial states made the avenue of making the economies of their colonies dependent on them. By implication, after the 'political independence' of the colonies, they still rely and dependent on their colonial masters for economic interventions and all. For example, every French colony till date adopts the currency of France, which clearly affirms the activeness of the French government in the affairs of their colonies. In short, neo-colonialism is the ground for affirming that independence which followed colonialism is just a political independence and not from external economic control, political dependence and even psychological enslavement. However, neo-colonialism is not the use of neither physical force nor violence but of strategy force and mental violence. Afisi (2017) avers that it involves the persistence of the colonial system in independent African states through transforming these nations into subjects of political, psychological, economic, social, military, and technological domination. This control is often exercised through indirect and subtle mechanisms, rather than through direct violence, which is today prevalent in most African nations (Wu, 2024). In essence, "Neo-colonialism is a more renewed form of traditional Colonialism, which is to gain, and benefit of those newly weak and decolonized countries with the goal of, achieving cultural, economic and political benefits by giving political power to those that belong to favorable elites" (Khodadadzadeh, 2017: 14). Inferably, neo-colonialism operates through capitalism through globalization, without the employment of physical force by economic slavery and a Eurocentric view over other cultures and tradition of their colonies. In other words, neo-colonialism can be said to be the discreet promotion of social, economic, and political

activities by former colonial powers, intended to strengthen capitalism, neoliberal globalization, and the cultural domination of their former colonies (Afisi, 2017).

The Concept of Decolonization

The concept of decolonization is clearly the clearing out of colonialism. Following the fact that it is the ruling out of colonialism or that which serves as a negation to the very idea of colonialism, it can be said to freedom of colonies from external controls. This concept specifically is a reaction to colonialism which once existed. In other words, this concept would never have existed if colonialism never occurred. The term decolonization involves an ideology that agitates for the true liberation of post-colonial Africa (Afisi, 2017). It could be identified as the elimination of colonial rule and the restoration of a nation's authority over its own territory. According to Afisi (2017), decolonization extends beyond mere independence from colonial rule to encompass complete liberation from the control and influence of imperial neo-colonialism, which also includes the capacity or determination of a formerly colonized nation to free itself from imperial dominance and manage its own domestic and international affairs. In other words, it aims to break people free from cultural and psychological subjugation imposed by foreign powers (Afisi, 2017). Hence, decolonization requires the dismantling of initially installed structures, belief system, and every other thing which emanated from the colonial masters into a more separate and distinct one in order to escape further torment in whatsoever form colonialism has decided to manifest itself in. In other words, the independence to be attained must as well include economic, psychological, structural, and political independence.

Decolonization to be precise is that which is mostly embarked upon by nationalist leaders, with the aim objective of setting free their nation which has suffered in the hands of external control, leaving their nation in a devastated state. Basically, the idea of decolonization can be effectively traced to the Africans. This however is as a result of their quest for freeing Africa from the chain it has long been captured with, which has made their culture and tradition more like an alien origin and some going into extinction. In other words, decolonization is having its root in revolt and rebellion against the idea of colonialism and everything surrounding it. The clamor is for a total replacement of the alien culture and tradition of the

colonial states with that of the indigenous culture and traditions. This implies that the quest for decolonization is a purposeful one and wasn't out of nothing. It is obvious that colonialism has always replaced the cultures of the indigenous people. Hence, it is arguable that decolonization will definitely seek to reawaken their indigenous ways of life. For the African case:

...the principle of individualism, believed to have been a European signature, seemed to have replaced the African cultural context of brotherhood, which suggests a welfare system of communalism, collectivism, and egalitarianism: hence, the need for a search for an ideology for decolonization... (Afisi, 2009: 33).

This however is not an easy task, for the colonial masters won't be willing to let go on a platter of gold due to the benefits they are receiving from the colonies. To this very effect, it is mostly to be achieved through the employment of force, which aligns with the position of Frantz Fanon (Peterson, 2021).

Fanon's Approach to Decolonization

Revolution has, over time, been classified as a necessity in the realization of a developed state. History has it that revolution has been the pioneer behind most civilization and development being enjoyed by most advanced states we see in our present clime, of which the U.S. revolutionary movement is a practical example. Hence, "Revolution is mankind's way of life today" (Fanon, 1970: 1). The birthing of the revolutionary movement on African soil was a reaction to colonialism, which distorted the development of the African people and their state. Following records, we had several African political leaders who decided to rebel against colonial oppression due to its colossal negative effects on the well-being of the people. Revolutionists like Kwame Nkrumah, Julius Nyerere, Obafemi Awolowo, Amilcar Carbral, Leopold Sedar Senghor, and Frantz Fanon amongst many others all saw the need to rebel against colonial rule to liberate the African people from the several kinds of slavery introduced by colonialism because, "Africa's post-colonial history is one of unfulfilled missions because the national leadership has been lacking in revolutionary theory and ideology (Noyou, 2014: 1). Hence, The Decolonization of African states became a common goal shared by these set of nationalist leaders. However, our concern in this very section has to do with that of Frantz Fanon.

The revolutionary process of Frantz Fanon was highly influenced by his overall experience of the machinery involved in the running of colonialism on the African soil, which is 'Violence'. His experience of the violence approach began when he was serving in the army to treat and attending to wounded soldiers. Therein, he experienced the violent approach initiated by the colonial masters just to get what they wanted, and their desire not to relent regarding going the extra mile to achieve the set goals of exploiting the African people to develop their metropolitan states. Accordingly, Fanon saw the excitement of the colonizers concerning the exploitation of their colonies, and not in any way ready to let go of the rope of colonialism since it replenishes their wealth. Hence, he concluded by positing that they have to be wiped out irrespective of their unwillingness to leave. To this effect, he proposed the very same way they came into power, which is through 'Violence'. What do we mean by violence? According to Mogaji (2024: 5), violence "... refers to some form of abuse, harm, or aggression, whether intentional as some would have it, or rather unintentional due to some sort of unawareness." It could also mean to violate, infringe upon, transgress, or exceed a certain limit, rights or norm (Buffachi, 2007). Whichever way, it connotes harm and violation of people if associated with humans.

To start with, it is important to familiarize ourselves with the idea of decolonization as the process of replacing some set of species with another group of species which is prone to causing chaos (Fanon, 1961). As expressed from the work of Fanon:

The naked truth of decolonisation evokes for us the searing bullets and bloodstained knives which emanate from it. For if the last shall be first, this will only come to pass after a murderous and decisive struggle between the two protagonists. That affirmed intention to place the last at the head of things, and to make them climb at a pace (too quickly, some say) the well-known steps which characterize an organized society, can only triumph if we use all means to turn the scale, including, of course, that of violence (Pallas, 2016).

Frantz Fanon as a nationalist has been an impactful one. He has "...for more than fifty years been a celebrated theorist, intellectual and activist of the black struggle for recognition, to the degree that he has assumed the status of a "sacred cow" in African nationalist discourse" (Settler, 2012: 5). His revolutionary theory has manifested in all of his over time but got decided upon in his work 'Wretched of the earth'. Deducing from his two previous

books, he exposed the gravity with which colonialism has dealt with the humanness of the Africans, its hidden goals and objectives, demonstrating how the people will get to be interested in overthrowing the so-called colonial rule. Hence, his work embodies a process political philosophy which at first explored the nature of colonialism, its effect, its consequences: if ignored, and as well the benefits involved if revolted against. In the *Wretched of the Earth*, Fanon exposed the adequate and plausible means of realizing the desired revolution which is through violence. Violence according to Fanon is the means by which the revolutionary movement can be successful. This idea emanated from the fact that colonialism came to be through a violent means, and hence, Fanon's approach agitates for the necessity of violence in extinguishing colonialism from Africa (Pallas, 2016). Fanon shows that the whole colonial project dominated its colonies by employing violence. In the expression of Pallas (2016), violence is the instrument through which the colonizing power sustains its control over the colonized population, which thus explains why Fanon emphasizes on the employment of violence as a necessity in the attempt of decolonisation. He also firmly believes that the French hold deeply flawed and misconceived notions about their colonized subjects, which ultimately lead to the dehumanization of Africans. In his view, the French perceive their colonized subjects as "the enemy of values, and in this sense, he is absolute evil" (Fanon, 1963: 41). This perspective suggests that Africans are stripped of their humanity and regarded as lacking any intrinsic value. Simply put, "the colonial subject is incapable of rational logic and comprehension, so must be dominated through the only means available: violence" (Pallas, 2016). Consequently, colonialism dehumanizes the colonized to such an extent that "it turns him into an animal" (Fanon, 1963: 42).

The way colonizers perceived and portrayed their colonized subjects played a significant role in shaping Fanon's concept of *Concerning Violence*. He explicitly argued that the liberation of the African people could only be achieved through violence, as it mirrored the very methods and approaches used by the colonizers to maintain their domination. As expressed by Fanon:

National liberation, national renaissance, the restoration of nationhood to the people, commonwealth: whatever may be the headings used or the new formulas introduced, decolonization is always a violent phenomenon. At whatever level we study it—relationships between individuals, new names for sports clubs, the

human admixture at cocktail parties, in the police, on the directing boards of national or private banks—decolonization is quite simply the replacing of a certain "species" of men by another "species" of men. Without any period of transition, there is a total, complete, and absolute substitution (Fanon, 1963: 35).

The process of colonization therefore in the idea of Fanon is not a peaceful one for it evokes chaos due to its adopted method of violence. Just as the process of colonialism is not a peaceful one, same condition binds the process of decolonization. In other words, "Decolonization, which sets out to change the order of the world, is, obviously, a program of complete disorder" (Fanon, 1963: 36). The historical process of decolonization has been expressed by Fanon to be that which does not happen unnoticed, neither does it occur without leaving its print on the course of history. That is: "...it cannot be understood, it cannot become intelligible nor clear to itself except in the exact measure that we can discern the movements which give it historical form and content" (Fanon, 1963: 36). Arguably, decolonization won't have been ascribed such relevance if colonialism did not precede its existence, or rather will not even dream to exist. To put differently, decolonization is certain to go through process for its actualization. Even, colonialism has been a planned-out endeavour which only got noticed in the final stage. It can all be traced back to slave trade. It's all a process. Fanon writes:

Decolonization is the veritable creation of new men. But this creation owes nothing of its legitimacy to any supernatural power: the "thing" which has been colonized becomes man during the same process by which it frees itself. In decolonization, there is therefore the need of a complete calling in question of the colonial situation. If we wish to describe it precisely, we might find it in the well-known words: "The last shall be first and the first last." Decolonization is the putting into practice of this sentence (Fanon, 1963: 36-37).

Therefore, violence in the view of Fanon is the machinery responsible for a successful liberation of the African people towards their desired nation free of: external control, loss of identity, dehumanization, and mental inferiority, suffered in the hands of colonialism. To Fanon, this is the only way out or no liberation can be attained because, "For the native, this violence represents the absolute line of action" (Fanon, 1963: 85).

A Critique of Fanon's Position Considering Current Realities

Frantz Fanon's advocacy for violent revolution as a means of decolonization remains one of the most debated aspects of his philosophy. His approach (model of revolutionary violence) which was built on the realities of colonial oppression was rather effective in the context of armed struggles for independence, which thence in today's reality requires critical reassessment in light of contemporary struggles for liberation. In contemporary society, the challenges faced by post-colonial states extend beyond direct colonial rule to neo-colonialism, economic dependence, political instability, and globalization, which cannot be effectively addressed through armed resistance as advertised by Fanon. Fanon's analysis of colonialism emphasized physical oppression; where colonial subjects were directly subjected to violence, forced labour, and cultural erasure, even when he mentioned the effect to have occurred on the structural and mental aspect. However, in the twenty-first century, the nature of oppression has shifted from direct colonial control to structural and economic dependencies, which is known today as neo-colonialism (Afisi, 2017). According to Afisi (2017), through the use of neo-colonialism, the former colonial powers continue to exert economic and political influence over African nations, ensuring that their economies remain dependent on foreign aid, multinational corporations, and exploitative trade agreements, which does not necessarily involve physical violence. As a matter of fact, contemporary struggles for liberation are not solely between an identifiable settler class and a colonized population, as was the case in Fanon's time, but rather, in involves internal governance failures, corruption, and elite complicity which have often been recorded to contribute immensely to post-colonial crisis (Noyoo, 2014). Many African leaders, once champions of anti-colonial struggles, have adopted authoritarian policies, oppressing their own people in ways that Fanon did not fully anticipate. In such contexts, a call for violent resistance risks plunging nations into cycles of internal conflict rather than fostering true liberation.

One of the major critiques of Fanon's revolutionary model is that while he effectively diagnosed the problem of colonialism, he provided limited guidance on post-revolution governance. His argument that "the last shall be first" (Fanon, 1963: 37) focuses on dismantling colonial structures but does not adequately address how to build stable, inclusive, and democratic institutions. As history has shown, many post-colonial states that achieved

independence through armed struggle later faced civil wars, military coups, and authoritarian rule, which tends to demonstrate that violence alone, cannot create a sustainable political system (Getachew, 2019). For context, countries such as Mali, Niger, and Burkina Faso which in our contemporary times uses violence for liberation struggles, have faced prolonged political instability and economic stagnation due to a lack of strong institutions and democratic governance. The focus on violence as a means to freedom often led to rule that births economic sabotage, poor international collaborations and political instability among many other vices. Thus, this raises a critical question: If violence can remove an oppressor, what ensures that the new leadership will govern justly and avoid replicating oppressive structures?

In today's world, effective resistance against neo-colonial structures requires more than armed confrontation. Scholars like Kwame Nkrumah (1965) have argued that intellectual decolonization, economic self-reliance, and cultural reclamation are more effective paths toward true independence. Neo-colonial control is exercised through economic policies, educational systems, and cultural narratives that perpetuate dependence on Western models (Khodadadzadeh, 2017). Addressing these issues requires reform in education, policy-making, and economic structures, rather than physical violence. Countries like Botswana and Ghana, which focused on institution-building, education, and economic development rather than armed conflict post-independence, have demonstrated relative political stability and growth. This suggests that modern struggles for African liberation should emphasize economic empowerment, intellectual sovereignty, and diplomatic resistance over violent confrontation, as it should have been observed in Burkina Faso and Niger.

However, despite these critiques, Fanon's work remains highly relevant in analysing the psychological impact of colonialism and the necessity of resistance against oppression. His ideas on alienation, identity, and cultural erasure still apply to modern issues of racial discrimination, global capitalism, and cultural imperialism; although, the contemporary struggle against oppression must adapt to the complexities of global power structures by incorporating strategies that goes beyond violence. Hence, rather than outright rejecting Fanon's theories, there is a need to reinterpret his ideas in a way that aligns with modern realities. Scholars like Ngūgī wa Thiong'o (1986) have expanded on Fanon's thought with emphases on the role of language, literature, and cultural production in resisting neo-colonialism.

Likewise, Amílcar Cabral (1966) proposed that true decolonization requires a cultural and intellectual awakening, rather than just military confrontation. In essence, we tend to submit that colonialism is no play at play, and as such, Fanon's approach needs to be revisited in order to conform to the present realities. Neo-colonialism, the modern version of colonialism is more of a strategic form of domination through trade and all of those, and should be faced with such strategic response. It does not need arms and whatever response must follow that strategic path, for arm war against neo-colonial masters is a war lost before it even started. Hence, we need to revisit Fanon's approach, redefine it to conform to current realities.

Conclusion

Having attempted an exposition of Frantz Fanon's critique of colonialism, which he identified as occurring through physical slavery, structural slavery, and mental slavery, it is evident that physical slavery led to both structural and psychological destruction. A philosophical analysis reveals that his approach of violence, which he advocated for in the decolonization of Africa, is somewhat inapplicable in our contemporary society. This position is so because, while colonialism still exists in another form (Neocolonialism), it no longer carries the direct influence, domination, or exploitation that characterized the colonial era. The new colonialism being experienced today must be addressed strategically. If Africa, or those still suffering from colonialism in today's society, are to achieve liberation, they must recognize that modern forms of control operate through economic dominance and capitalist influence, which are often perpetuated and facilitated by international institutions. While violence has historically been used as a mode of decolonization, it may not be the best approach at this point in time. Instead, we recommend a more subtle and strategic form of resistance, taking into consideration the consequences of resorting to physical violence. Given that most technical knowledge and advanced technologies are controlled by global powers; the neo-colonial masters of today—engaging in direct economic or political warfare with them could be counterproductive. Therefore, it would be more advisable to pursue strategic resistance by building relationships with these powers while remaining cautious and conscious of the benefits and potential outcomes of any collaboration or partnership. As a result, any attempt at liberation must be reformed. We have suggested that efforts towards liberation must shift from

violence to strategic responses. We argue that, as contemporary demands for liberation continue to rise, revolutionary actions must align with current realities, as a violent confrontation against neo-colonial powers is doomed to fail before it even begins. Therefore, any response must take a strategic, non-violent approach, which makes it essential to revisit Fanon's perspective and adapt it to align with contemporary realities.

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